

QUIZ

LAST NAME: Laux

FIRST NAME: Elda

PROGRAM CODE: LLM

COURSE CODE : ACA-401

PERIOD NUMBER: 6

INSTRUCTOR: Gulma

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. Differences between UK and US English:

- In British usage, punctuation always goes inside quote; in American usage, it can go either inside or outside
- In American usage, punctuation always goes inside quote; in British usage, it can go either inside or outside¹**
- In British usage, punctuation goes outside quote; in American usage, it can go either inside or outside
- In American usage, punctuation goes outside quote; in British usage, it can go either inside or outside

2. According to the Chicago Manual of Style, which of the following bibliographic format is correct?

¹ Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 2nd ed. (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University), 2019

- Booth, Wayne C., Gregory G. Colomb, and Joseph M. Williams. *The Craft of Research*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1995
- Booth, Wayne C., Gregory G. Colomb, and Joseph M. Williams. *The Craft of Research*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1995**
Booth, Wayne C. Gregory G. Colomb, and Joseph M. Williams. *The Craft of Research*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1995²
- Booth, Wayne C. Gregory G. Colomb, and Joseph M. Williams. *The Craft of Research*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1995
- Booth Wayne C., Gregory G. Colomb and Joseph M. Williams. *The Craft of Research*. Chicago. University of Chicago Press. 1995

3. **On which criteria should the sources we find, be skimmed on?**

- Relevance and transparency
- Pragmatism and ease of access
- Relevance and reliability³**
- Transparency and pragmatism

4. **Which are the general goals of the research?**

- Ask a question worth answering
- Find an answer that can be supported with good reasons
- Find good evidence
- Draft an argument that makes a good case for the answer, and

² EUCLID, *ACA-401 Coursepack. Period 1* (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University 2019), 55

³ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Paper, Theses and Dissertation. Ninth Edition. Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, ed. Wayne C. Booth et.al., Ninth Edition (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 28

Revise the draft until readers think the goals are met

All of the above⁴

5. **Once having a final draft, we start writing the final introduction and conclusion. How many aims does the introduction have?**

Put the research in context of another research

make readers understand how the paper addresses a problem they care about

give them a framework to understand it

All of the above⁵

6. **Why should we cite?**

to give credit

to reassure readers of the accuracy of our work

to show readers the research tradition that informs the own work, and

to help readers follow or extend the research

All of the above⁶

7. **When do we use “supra” and “hereinafter?”**

⁴ Kate L. Turabian, 10

⁵ Kate L. Turabian, 107

⁶ Kate L. Turabian, 135

- When we refer to legislative hearings, court filings, books and so on⁷**
- When we refer to statutes, constitutions, regulations and more
- When we refer to different sources from internet
- None of the above

8. **How can a legal citation be used?**

- A legal citation can be used in citation sentence and citation clause⁸**
- A legal citation can be used only in a citation sentence
- A legal citation can be used only in citation clause
- None of the above

9. **To point the reader to the specific pages that relate to the cited proposition, we must include a pinpoint citation, often called a “pincite.” Where are the pincites placed?⁹**

- The pincites are placed after the page on which the case report begins, separated by a comma**
- The pincites are placed after the page on which the case report begins, separated by a colon
- The pincites are placed after the page on which the case report begins, separated by a semicolon

⁷ *The Bluebook: A Uniform System of Citation*. 20th ed., (Cambridge, Massachusetts: Ganett House, 2015), 8

⁸ *The Bluebook*, 4

⁹ *The Bluebook*, 12-13

- The pincites are placed after the page on which the case report begins, separated by a hyphen

10. **Explanatory parenthetical information begins with:**

- A capital letter and present participle
- A capital letter and past participle
- Small letter and present participle
- With a present participle and never a capital letter¹⁰**

11. **The signals we use when writing legally show:**

- Support: e.g., accord, see, see also
- Contradiction: contra, but see, but cf.
- Background material: see generally
- All of the above¹¹**

¹⁰ The Bluebook, 64

¹¹ The Bluebook, 58-60

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 2nd ed. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019.
- Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 4*. 2nd ed. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2020.
- Columbia Law Review Association, the Harvard Law Review Association, the University of Pennsylvania Law Review, and the Yale Law Journal. 20th ed. *The Bluebook: A Uniform System of Citation*. Cambridge, Massachusetts: Ganett House, 2015.
- Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Edited by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, William T. FitzGerald, and The University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff. Ninth edition. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.